

SMART ERA

Report on data screening and joint data-driven analysis / D2.2

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Author(s)	Ossi Kotavaara (UOULU), Marton Magyar (UOULU), Pauliina Björk, (UOULU), Jorge Martinez-Gil (SCCH) & Aleksei Karetnikov (SCCH)
Reviewers	Antonio Salvator Filograna (ENG), Tjaša Heričko (UM)
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v	Date	Contributor(s)	Comment
0.1	05/12/2025	Ossi Kotavaara (UOULU), Marton Magyar (UOULU), Pauliina Björk, (UOULU), Jorge Martinez-Gil (SCCH), Aleksei Karetnikov (SCCH)	Version submitted to internal review.
0.2	16/12/2025	Antonio Salvator Filograna (ENG) & Tjaša Heričko (UM)	Review of the document.
0.3	19/12/2025	Ossi Kotavaara (UOULU), Marton Magyar (UOULU), Pauliina Björk, (UOULU), Jorge Martinez-Gil (SCCH), Aleksei Karetnikov (SCCH)	Integration of feedback. Version submitted to coordinator's review.
1.0	22/12/2025	Matteo Gerosa (FBK), Alessia Torre (FBK)	Final quality check, editing and submission.

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Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial intelligence
BI	Business Intelligence
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
CSV	A plain text data format for tabular data
D	Deliverable
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
EV	Electric vehicle
GeoJSON	An open standard format for geographical features with their attributes
GI	Geographical Intelligence
GIS	Geographic information systems
GTFS	General Transit Feed Specification
ICT	Information and communication technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LLM	Large language models
LAU	Local Administrative Units
NLG	Natural Language Generation
NEET	Neither in employment nor in education
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OSM	OpenStreetMap
POI	Point of interest
SESAM	SMART ERA Smartness Assessment Method
T	Task
WFS	Web Feature Service
WP	Work package

1. Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.2 – “Report on data screening and joint data-driven analysis” presents the outcomes of data screening and joint data-driven analyses carried out within SMART ERA Work Package 2 (WP2), supporting the implementation of the SMART ERA Smartness Assessment Method (SESAM). The purpose of this work is to establish a robust, scalable and evidence-based approach for assessing the smartness and socio-economic dynamics of rural areas across Europe and to prepare the methodological foundations for future large-scale deployment.

First, the report focuses on a systematic screening and evaluation of spatial and statistical data relevant for SESAM’s six smartness dimensions: Enabling Factors, Mobility and Transport, Economy, Governance and Policy, Services of General Interest, and Environment and Climate-Related SDGs. The screening prioritised 80 openly accessible European wide datasets. Key datasets include NUTS-level information from the Eurostat database, 1×1 km grid population data, OpenStreetMap services, transport network data and General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) public transport data. Crowd-sourced mobile network information was also obtained from OpenCellID. Particular attention was given to ensuring that the data was applicable across the six SMART ERA pilot regions.

The second main focus area of the report is introducing methods for SESAM joint data-driven analysis, in which spatial data as well as artificial intelligence (AI), and especially large language models (LLMs), play a central role. SESAM is supported by local scale spatial analyses based on geographic information science. Key methods are GIS-based multimodal accessibility and infrastructure analyses as well as digital connectivity assessments, which provide high-resolution indicators of physical and digital access to key rural services with a high accuracy as well as replicability and scalability. These indicators are then integrated into an AI-supported pipeline that automates interpretation and reporting.

Instead of treating AI as a separate add-on, SMART ERA embeds LLMs directly in the analytical workflow to transform complex geospatial and statistical outputs into consistent, human-readable smartness narratives tailored to each pilot region. To enable this, the project has developed a modular architecture combining a standardised data pipeline with an AI module for data-to-text generation. The LLM component is configured with strict fact-selection and verification steps to keep generated text traceable to underlying indicators improving reliability for planning and policy use. The resulting reports and interactive applications offer local stakeholders a unified entry point to explore SESAM indicators, understand strengths and gaps, and compare their situation with other regions without needing advanced technical expertise.

Together, these efforts create a coherent and transferable AI-enhanced analytical framework that strengthens the quantitative foundations of SESAM. The results form a baseline for subsequent evaluation, co-design activities and policy guidance, enabling SMART ERA pilot regions and other European rural communities to assess their smartness maturity and plan data-driven, AI-assisted transitions toward more sustainable and resilient futures.

2. Introduction

2.1 Directions from SMART ERA Smartness Assessment Method (SESAM)

In addition to the SMART ERA project plan, the aim and target setting for this deliverable is set particularly by SMART ERA deliverable 2.1 “Smartness Assessment methodology” by Consorzio Poliedra et al. (2024) later referred as D2.1. The work reported in this deliverable is conducted in SMART ERA tasks T2.2 “Data screening for designing a joint rural data-driven approach” and T2.3 “Joint data-driven analyses to pilot/study regions” as a part of SMART ERA Work Package 2 (WP2), which goals are to create a multi-dimensional methodology to investigate the smartness and socio-economic dynamics in rural areas. The final objective is to build the first large-scale European-wide methodology for the assessment of needs for smartness transition in rural areas and for the selection of innovation actions to be co-designed and implemented. The approach provides an integrated methodology to i) enable rural regions to assess their maturity in smartness; ii) benchmark smartness between regions and; iii) develop feasible actions to foster smartness through the adoption of the SIPs and with place-based and regional policies.

The SMART ERA Smartness Assessment Method (SESAM) is designed to provide a comprehensive qualitative and quantitative framework for evaluating the smart development of rural territories (D2.1). Its core aim is to help rural and mountain areas assess their current smartness maturity, identify strengths and gaps, and set priorities for future development. SESAM provides the conceptual and methodological framework that guides our quantitative data screening and analysis reported in this deliverable. The approach is focused on six smartness dimensions: 1) Enabling Factors, 2) Mobility and Transport, 3) Economy, 4) Governance and Policy, 5) Services of General Interest, and 6) Environment and Climate-Related SDGs.

SESAM (D2.1) defines rural smartness as a multidimensional construct rooted in digital transformation, sustainability, service provision, governance and the overall socio-economic vitality of rural areas. In order to support evidence-based decision-making, SESAM uses and combines quantitative and qualitative methods and data. SESAM provides an opportunity to utilise an extensive tailored selection of quantitative indicators designed to produce measurable and comparable analysis of smartness. SESAM identifies status indicators for different dimensions, that can be used to reflect and benchmark the current conditions of smartness maturity in rural communities. These indicators are suggested to be supported by standardised metrics to capture performance objectively and also enable continuous monitoring over time. Emphasis is placed on the RACER criteria ensuring indicators are Relevant, Accepted, Credible, Easy to monitor, and Robust (see e.g. Working group on Performance Measurement..., 2017; D2.1), so they can function effectively across diverse rural development contexts.

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In alignment with SESAM, the conducted quantitative data screening systematically evaluates available spatial and statistical data that correspond to these status indicators and have potential to be scaled up or extrapolated to other European rural regions. SESAM provides data and methodological directions for the data screening and analyses, whereas availability of the data set the limits. SESAM provides clear data and methodological directions for structuring the data screening and providing supplementary analyses for rural smartness. While SESAM sets out what should ideally be measured, the availability, granularity, and quality of data ultimately define what can be measured in practice. Some indicators benefit from robust data coverage across Europe including e.g. services, infrastructure, demographic and socio-economic patterns, development of industries, while other factors particularly those linked to governance, policies, digital literacy and SDGs are needed to be analysed in qualitative framework to achieve needed quality.

2.2 Aims of Systematic Data Screening and Assessment

T2.2 “Data screening for designing a joint rural data-driven approach” conducted a systematic screening of data sources that could be used to analyse smartness and socio-economic dynamics in rural areas. The emphasis was on data that supports the availability and scalability of European rural areas, with a special focus on data that follows the FAIR principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability, or data that is licensed under Creative Commons attribution license CC BY 4.0 or some other comparable licensing.

Work consisted of exploring 1) data availability including open, commercial, research or official use licensed sources; 2) assessment of data quality including data providers e.g., statistical centres, official registers, other public sector actors, companies, research, crowd-sourced; 3) temporal resolution i.e., update frequency and timeliness i.e., how recent data is available; 4) geographic coverage and spatial resolution from larger administrative scales (NUTS 3 and LAU 1-2) to small area statistics (such as postal code regions and grid cells); and 5) potential data fees. The work in progress in the SMART ERA was supported with internal technical notes, whereas this deliverable is the final and public document. Selected data sources will complement the data already available from SMART ERA deliverable 5.1 “Pilot needs and gap analysis” by AnySolution et al. (2024) later referred as D5.1.

The aim of the systematic data screening and assessment process is to ensure that SESAM’s quantitative analysis can be consistently replicated within diverse rural territories and scaled to the European level while maintaining sufficient local-scale accuracy and applicability. By building indicators largely based on standardized and openly accessible datasets, when possible, the comparability and transparency of results between regions can be supported while minimising data-processing and harmonizing efforts. In quantitative register-based data analysis in WP2, only already aggregated and k-anonymised data related to population are used in order to ensure that all analytical phases and outputs rely solely on non-sensitive privacy-preserving information suitable for comparative analysis across rural territories.

During the data screening process, special attention was given to geographic and temporal coverage and spatial resolution of the data. European and global datasets are prioritized as

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primary sources to ensure comparability and scalability. In addition, potential licensing costs or usage restrictions were inspected to ensure long-term sustainability and accessibility of selected data sources. The available data ranges from larger administrative scales, such as NUTS 2-3 and LAU 1-2, to high-resolution data at grid-cell or precise location scales. Key data entities screened are Eurostat's databased at NUTS 2-3 scales and population and housing data at 1x1 km resolution supplemented with national data from Bosnia and Herzegovina. Other key data sources screened are OpenStreetMap (OSM) including roads, bike and walking lanes as well as large selection of services and amenities; and General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) data enables accurate spatio-temporal multimodal public transport analysis. Moreover, The OpenCellid API, providing crowd-sourced mobile network data under a Creative Commons license, adds an important layer for measuring digital connectivity and infrastructure. The project has also developed workflows and technical methods to correct and open-source process spatial data. For example, street network topologies extracted from OpenStreetMap are being refined to ensure they are routable, which is essential for accessibility analyses. This report covers over 80 data sources screened for SESAM.

To facilitate the integration and dissemination of geospatial data, a GeoServer environment has been established by UOULU. This platform allows for sharing raster and vector spatial datasets via Web Feature Services (WFS), supporting the visualization and distribution of analytical outputs.

2.3 Aims of Joint Data-Driven Analysis with Integrated Data and AI

Within Task T2.3, "Joint data-driven analyses to pilot/study regions" the project deploys an LLM alongside other tools to decode smartness indicators. Technical teams prepare and calibrate these models to recognize specific patterns within rural datasets. The idea is to generate written summaries that convert abstract statistics into actionable descriptions for municipal planners and decision-makers. These automated reports allow stakeholders to grasp data implications without requiring specialized technical training. All generated content populates the central data web application directly. This automated pipeline creates a replicable standard, allowing diverse European rural regions to apply the same analytical logic to their own local territories.

SMART ERA pilot areas will serve as first users and validation environments for the analyses, enabling SESAM to evolve into a reliable and repeatable framework that can eventually be applied across EU and beyond.

3. European Statistical Divisions and Systems from the Perspective of SMART ERA

As the EU's statistical authority, Eurostat coordinates statistical activities across the EU's institutions and bodies, and is responsible to develop, produce, disseminate, and coordinate European statistics. Eurostat's regional data largely covers European Union regions, as well as the EFTA countries of Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway and Switzerland. Data for EU enlargement countries including Bosnia and Herzegovina, are available to a limited extent.

The Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) is the European Union's standardized hierarchical system for dividing member states into comparable statistical regions, supporting regional analysis and the allocation of EU cohesion policies. It consists of three levels: NUTS 1 for major socio-economic regions, NUTS 2 for basic regions for regional policies, and NUTS 3 for small regions for specific diagnoses) (Eurostat 2025b). Depending on population density and sizes of the countries, the spatial extent of the NUTS regions may vary significantly.

In a more accurate scale below NUTS, the Local Administrative Units (LAU) classification represents the municipal and communes level, offering finer-scale statistical representing subdivisions of NUTS 3 regions and serving as the basis for local typologies. Since 2017, the system has consisted of a single LAU level. Before that, there were additional LAU 1 and LAU 2 levels, with LAU 2 being comparable to LAU today. LAU is useful for local planning and service delivery (Eurostat 2025a). Together, NUTS and LAU ensure harmonized regional and local statistics across Europe and enable consistent socio-economic comparisons and support policy evaluation. However, for example, data is provided most largely on NUTS levels by Eurostat.

Population grid cell data (or gridded population data or population grid data) refers to population counts or densities mapped onto a grid instead of being administrative boundaries. For example, Eurostat population data is available in 1 km × 1 km grid cells (Eurostat 2025c). In some countries, such as Finland, socio-economic, housing and building data is available in grid cell format as well (Finnish Environment Institute 2025). Grid cell data have several advantages as they provide a spatially continuous representation of population or other available attribute, which makes it easier to combine population data with other spatial data.

The SMART ERA pilots are geographically distributed over six different European countries (five EU member states and one in a candidate status) as presented in Figure 1. Background information of the SMART ERA pilot sites with larger local and regional description of different is provided in SMART ERA deliverable 5.1 "Pilot needs and gap analysis" by AnySolution et al. (2024), later referred as D5.1. In addition to global and European wide data, national statistics can be used to enrich SESAM indicators.

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Pilot region 1, Valle di Sole, Italy, is covered by Italy's national statistical system ISTAT¹ for demographic, economic, and tourism data, with local authorities contributing through e.g., open data Trentino². ISTAT is the largest producer of open data in Italy promoting transparency and reuse and engages in extensive European collaboration through research projects, data harmonization, and technical assistance, working with Eurostat, universities, and other national statistical offices

Pilot region 2, Sóller/Tramuntana, Spain is covered by National Statistics Institute, Spain i.e., Instituto Nacional de Estadística INE³, and also by Balearic Islands specialised Instituto de Estadística de las Islas Baleares (IBESTAT)⁴ for socio-economic and environmental indicators, especially related to protected natural areas. Collaborating with Eurostat and EU member states within the European Statistical System, the INE also partners with international statistical organizations to jointly design and implement projects of common interest.

Pilot region 3, Northern Ostrobothnia, Finland is covered by Statistics Finland i.e., Tilastokeskus statistical data⁵ and spatial data⁶, as well as individual and enterprise level microdata⁷ services and datasets on population, industries, and environmental monitoring. Finland's strong open-data policy ensures wide public access under clear licensing and privacy rules. However, in some cases, spatial and municipal data usage is licenced with a fee or restricted and protected with regulations. Statistics Finland and several other Finnish government agencies produce statistics for the policy needs of the European Union in accordance with the requirements of the European Union's Statistical Programme and the European Statistical System

Pilot region 4, Trebinje, East Herzegovina, Bosnia and Herzegovina is covered by the Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina⁸ and Republika Srpska Institute of Statistics⁹. The activities of International Cooperation are aimed at enhancing the quality and comparability of official statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina and increasing compliance with EU and UN standards. The Agency represents the statistical system of BiH, which includes the Entity Institutes the Institute for Statistics of FBiH and the Institute for Statistics of Republika Srpska.

Pilot region 5, Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia, is covered by Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia (SURS) i.e., Statistični urad Republike Slovenije¹⁰ and municipal reporting systems for agricultural, demographic, and rural-development data. SURS is a member of the

¹ ISTAT Databases <https://www.istat.it/en/data/databases/>

² Open data Trentino <https://dati.trentino.it/dataset>

³ Instituto Nacional de Estadística <https://www.ine.es/en/>

⁴ Instituto de Estadística de las Islas Baleares (IBESTAT) <https://ibestat.es/>

⁵ Statistics Finland, Statistics Finland's free-of-charge statistical databases, <https://pxdata.stat.fi/PxWeb/pxweb/en/StatFin/>

⁶ Statistics Finland, Open geographic data, https://stat.fi/tup/avoin-data/paikkatietoaineistot_en.html

⁷ Statistics Finland, Taika - research data catalogue, <https://taika.stat.fi/en/>

⁸ Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina, <https://bhas.gov.ba/?lang=en>

⁹ Republika Srpska Institute of Statistics, <https://www.rzs.rs.ba/>

¹⁰ Statistični urad Republike Slovenije <https://pxweb.stat.si/SiStat/en>

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European Statistical System and in this role actively cooperates in working groups and committees of Eurostat, the Statistical Office of the European Union, and in technical and infrastructural projects coordinated by Eurostat.

Pilot region 6, Devetaki Plateau, Bulgaria is covered by Bulgaria's National Statistical Institute (NSI)¹¹, with local environmental and rural-development data supplemented by regional authorities. NSI is a member of the European Statistical System (ESS), cooperating with Eurostat and other national statistical authorities to produce harmonised, comparable European-level statistics.

¹¹ National Statistical Institute (NSI), Bulgaria, <https://www.nsi.bg/en/>

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Figure 1. SMART ERA pilot regions within LAU, NUTS 3 and NUTS 2 regional-statistical divisions.

4. Systematic Data Screening and Assessment for Rural Smartness Analysis

4.1 Regional NUTS 2-3 Scale Data by Eurostat

This subsection presents the systematic screening of Eurostat regional datasets at NUTS 2 and NUTS 3 levels that are relevant for the quantitative implementation of SESAM. Eurostat data provides harmonised, comparable and regularly updated regional statistics across Europe, making them a solid basis for cross-regional rural smartness analysis. At the same time, the use of these administrative scales implies limitations for capturing intra-regional variation in sparsely populated or heterogeneous rural areas. Direct, indirect and supportive usage of the data is considered by different SESAM indicators organised under the six smartness dimensions: 1) Enabling Factors, 2) Mobility and Transport, 3) Economy, 4) Governance and Policy, 5) Services of General Interest, and 6) Environment and Climate-Related SDGs. The associated datasets, their temporal coverage, NUTS-level spatial resolution, and access links are provided in tables. Eurostat datasets are referenced using their official dataset titles and identifiers.

4.1.1 Enabling Factors

Level of digital connectivity status indicator measures the availability and quality of digital network connections within a rural community. Households with access to internet from home and with broadband access measure these directly. However, the percentage at NUTS 2 level, especially if it is low, does not fully address the digital connectivity of smaller rural areas.

The sub-dimension of *digital literacy* evaluates the ICT skill levels within rural communities, reflecting their technical proficiency. There is no direct measure to this, but frequency of most common digital services can be used as indirect measure. Also, never using internet can be used as countermeasure.

The dataset, which is listed in following under digital literacy, “Individuals who used the internet for interaction with public authorities (last 12 months)”, can be used also to evaluate the under the *governance and policy* dimension and public governance sub-dimension, the indicator *Level of Online Service Accessibility* evaluating availability and usability of online public services for citizens and businesses.

Digital infrastructure and digital literacy related datasets cover all the pilot regions except Bosnia and Herzegovina. Coverage of the rest of Europe is partial; for example, Germany is missing from all of these datasets.

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Table 1. Digital infrastructure related data relevant for SESAM in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Level of digital connectivity	Households with access to the internet at home	2006-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_IACC_H
	Households with broadband access	2006-2021	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_BROAD_H

Table 2. Digital literacy related data relevant for SESAM in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Technical proficiency of rural populations	Individuals who used the internet: Frequency of access: daily	2006-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_IU_SE_I
	Individuals who used the internet: Frequency of access: once a week (including every day)			
	Individuals who used the internet: Participating in social networks (creating user profile, posting messages or other contributions to facebook, twitter, etc.)			
	Individuals who used the internet: Internet banking			
	Individuals who used the internet: Selling goods or services			
	Individuals who used the internet: Civic or political participation			
	Individuals who used the internet: never			
	Individuals who used the internet for interaction with public authorities (last 12 months)	2006-2021	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_IU_SE_I
	Individuals who ordered goods or services over the internet for private use. Last online purchase in 3 months	2006-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_IU_SE_I
	Individuals who ordered goods or services over the internet for private			

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	use. Online purchases: travel and holiday accommodation			
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4.1.2 Mobility and Transport

The *low-carbon fuel vehicles* indicator assesses the adoption and use of vehicles powered by low-carbon or renewable fuels, such as electric vehicles (EVs), plug-in hybrids, or vehicles running on biodiesel, in rural areas. This dataset fits this indicator directly, but the NUTS 2 scale may again hide the number of electric vehicles in rural areas. The dataset covers all the pilot areas except Bosnia and Herzegovina, and the European coverage is good.

Table 3. Mobility and Transport related data relevant for SESAM in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Mobility methods and vehicles used for this purpose: Low-carbon fuel vehicles	Stock of electric vehicles by category: Goods road motor vehicles <= 3.5 tonnes	2018-2023	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/TRAN_R_ELVEHST
	Passenger cars			
	Buses, motor coaches, and trolley buses			

4.1.3 Economy

Economy dimension's sub-dimensions *primary sector* the dataset "Beneficiary of rural development support measures by legal form, economic size and farm type of the agricultural holding" provides several subsets of data on indicator *presence of circular agricultural practices*, which assesses the implementation of sustainable practices, such as waste reduction and resource recycling, e.g., investments for afforestation, improvement of resilience in forestry, agroforestry and organic farming. Also, in the same dataset there are subsets useful for measuring the indicator *level of investment in innovative agriculture*, e.g., investments in forest technologies and processing, risk management; knowledge exchange and dissemination of information; investments to add value to agricultural products, received farm advisory services; and cooperation to support quality schemes. Coverage for the most recently available year (2023) is poor, but coverage of the pilot areas and the rest of Europe is better for the previous year (2020). However, coverage for Spain, Slovenia and Bosnia and Herzegovina is missing.

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Table 4. Primary sector related data relevant for SESAM in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Presence of circular agricultural practices	Beneficiary of rural development support measures by legal form, economic size and farm type of the agricultural holding:	2010-2023	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/EF_RD_LEG
Level of investment in innovative agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments for afforestation • Investments for the establishment of agroforestry • Investments for the improvement of resilience in forestry • Investments in forest technologies and processing • Investments for the restoration of damage to agricultural or forestry production • Investments to add value to agricultural products • Commitments for animal welfare • Commitments for organic farming • Commitments for environment and climate related to existing forest land • Habitats Directive - Natura 2000 • Water framework Directive • Risk management: Knowledge exchange and dissemination of information • Received farm advisory services • Cooperation to support quality schemes 			

Eurostat has several datasets on firms' ICT usage at the NUTS 2 level, covering the use of the internet in general, cloud services, AI, digital invoicing, enterprise resource planning (ERP), customer relationship management (CRM), business intelligence (BI), web sales, and data analytics. Firms can be categorised by sector. However, these datasets only cover firms with more than 10 employees. These datasets have poor coverage of Europe, and the coverage of the pilot regions is partial, as only Spain and Slovenia are covered. Some datasets do not have data for the latest year, 2024, but have data for 2023.

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Table 5. Enterprise (and also their digital literacy) related data in Eurostat database relevant for SESAM in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Level of digitalisation and ICT skills of the employees (Only for firms larger than 10 employees)	Use of computers and the internet by employees, by sector	2023-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_CI_CM_PN2
	Firm's internet access by sector	2023-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_CI_IN_EN2
	Firm's use of cloud computing services by sector	2023-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_CICCE_USEN2
	Firm's use of AI services by sector	2023-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_EB_AIN2
	Firms supply chain management: digital invoicing, by sector	2023	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_EB_ICSN2
	Firms using ERP, CRM or BI software, by sector	2023	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_EB_IIPN2
	Firms with web sales, by sector	2023	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_EC_ESELN2
	Firm's turnover of web sales	2023	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_EC_EVALN2
	Firms using data-analytics	2023-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_EB_DAN2

The business demography dataset provides basic information at the NUTS 3 level, including the number and size of firms, new enterprises, enterprise churn and job creation, alongside sector information. The dataset has good coverage across Europe and the pilot regions, with the exception of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Table 6. Business demography data in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Supportive information: number of firms in primary, secondary and tertiary sector	Business demography: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • number of enterprises, • new enterprises, • churn of enterprises, • jobs in enterprises, • jobs in new enterprises (Enterprises are available total or by sector.)	2013-2022	NUTS 3	https://doi.org/10.2908/BD_HGNACE_R

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	Employer business demography <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enterprises having at least one employee • Enterprises having the first employee • Survivals of enterprises having at least one employee (3-calendar year survival only) • Employer enterprises business churn • Birth rate of employer enterprises 	2013-2024	NUTS 3	https://doi.org/10.2908/BD_SALGE1_NACE_R
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4.1.4 Governance and Policy

For dimension *governance and policy* and sub-dimension of *public governance*, data for direct and indirect measures is limitedly available in Eurostat database. *Level of online service accessibility* and *availability and usability of online public services for citizens and businesses* can be evaluated based on the same dataset listed currently under Digital literacy: “Individuals who used the internet for interaction with public authorities (last 12 months)”. The dataset has good coverage of the pilot regions, except for Bosnia and Herzegovina. For the EU, however, the coverage is partial.

Table 7. Data on internet usage for interaction with public authorities in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Level of online service accessibility	Individuals who used the internet for interaction with public authorities (last 12 months)	2006-2021	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ISO_C_R_GOV_I

4.1.5 Services of General Interest

For the dimension of the *services of general interest* and sub-dimension *education*, “Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools” can be used to evaluate the integration and use of digital technologies in rural educational institutions, with the aim of improving learning outcomes and accessibility. Eurostat data provides useful background information on digitalisation. Participation rates in education and the number of students in higher education provide an indication of educational coverage, while the NEET (Not in Education, Employment or

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Training) rate illustrates the other aspects of young people's lives. The datasets cover the pilot regions well, except for Bosnia and Herzegovina, and also cover Europe well.

Table 8. Education related data in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Education related supportive information	Participation rates in selected education levels at regional level	2012-2023	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/EDUC_UOE_ENRA15
	Students enrolled in tertiary education by education level, program orientation, sex and region	2013-2023	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/EDUC_UOE_ENRT06
	Young people neither in employment nor in education and training by sex and region (NEET rates)	2000-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/EDAT_LFSE_22

Eurostat provides a dataset on hospital beds and physicians at the NUTS 2 level. This information can be used to assess the capacity of physical healthcare services, which can be supplemented by digital services. The dataset on self-reported unmet needs for medical examinations at NUTS 2 level reveals interesting insights into the reasons for unmet needs, such as distance, cost and waiting times. While these datasets provide good coverage of the pilot regions, they do not cover Bosnia and Herzegovina, and the coverage of the rest of Europe is also partial. Data on hospital beds and physicians is available for 2023.

Table 9. Health care related data relevant for SESAM in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Health care related supportive information	Self-reported unmet needs for medical examination by main reason declared: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Too far to travel • Too expensive • Waiting list 	2015-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/HLTH_SILC_08_R
	Hospital beds	2015-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/HLTH_RS_BDSRG2
	Physicians	2015-2024	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/HLTH_RS_PHYSREG

4.1.6 Environment and Environmental and Climate-Related SDGs

There is a lack of data related to dimension of *Environment and Environmental and Climate-Related SDGs*. Available data

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is connected to sub-dimension of *development of a resource-efficient, low-carbon economy topic* and indicator *status of smart waste and recycling management* and definition, can be evaluated using Eurostat dataset of Number and capacity of recovery and disposal facilities. The data includes recycling, incineration and backfilling together with less smarter options like landfill, which can be used as negative indicators. The temporal coverage of this dataset is poor, there is no updated data after year 2008.

Table 10. Waste and Recycling related data relevant for SESAM in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Status of smart waste and recycling management	Number and capacity of recovery and disposal facilities	2004-2022	NUTS 2	https://doi.org/10.2908/ENV_WASFAC

4.1.7 Background and Contextual Information Datasets

The population structure and population change, labour force and employment at NUTS 3 level provide useful background information on the socio-economic characteristics of the region. The labour force dataset has good coverage for the pilot regions and Europe in general in 2022, as well as for the population structure and change datasets in 2024. However, Bosnia and Herzegovina is not included in the data.

Table 11. Population and socio-economic data in Eurostat database.

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Supportive information	Labor force and employment status: Employed persons, total or by sector	1995-2024	NUTS 3	https://doi.org/10.2908/NA_MA_10R_3EMPERS
	Population structure indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age dependency ratio • Median age of population • Woman to men ratio 	2014-2024	NUTS 3	https://doi.org/10.2908/dem_o_r_pjanind3
	Population change - Demographic balance and crude rates: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crude birth rate • Net migration 	2000-2024	NUTS 3	https://doi.org/10.2908/dem_o_r_gind3

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4.2 Supplementary Regional Data at NUTS 2-3 Levels by Republika Srpska Institute of Statistics

Republika Srpska Institute of Statistics (2024) provided key background and contextual variables in its statistical publication, which can be used as a supplementary data for Eurostat data for the pilot region 4, Trebinje, East Herzegovina, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Table 12. Population and socio-economic figures available by Republika Srpska Institute of Statistics (2024).

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Population	Total population estimate 2023	2023	Municipality	PDF chapter 1.1
	Population by age group etc, census 2013	2013	Municipality	PDF chapter 4.1
	Households by number of members	2013	Municipality	PDF chapter 4.4
	Population estimates by age groups etc	2023	Municipality	PDF chapter 4.7
Labour force	Number of employed persons	2023	Municipality	PDF chapter 1.1
	Number of persons seeking for employment	2023	Municipality	PDF chapter 1.1

Table 13. Business demography figures available by Republika Srpska Institute of Statistics (2024).

Indicator	Dataset	Years	Scale	Link to data
Business demography	Number of business entities	2019-2023	Municipality	PDF chapter 3.1
	Number of business entities by legal form	2023	Municipality	PDF chapter 3.2
	Number of business entities by sector	2023	Municipality	PDF chapter 3.2

4.3 Services and Amenities Data in OpenStreetMap

The OpenStreetMap (OSM) database includes rich data on accurately located services and amenities contributed by a global community of volunteer mappers and official governmental bodies. In OSM, points of interest (POI) are locations with attributes, such as a shop, a postbox, or a tourist attraction that is represented by a single point rather than by an area or a line (OpenStreetMap 2025a). These features help describe the geographic availability of the services and amenities, such as key everyday services such as, grocery stores and supermarkets, postal services or charging stations as well as health care services, restaurants, banks, shops, internet coffees or transportation hubs. Public services and amenities such as libraries, hospitals, schools, toilets, drinking water posts or parks are also

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widely recorded. All POIs are tagged using a partly curated but largely flexible schema which allows for detailed region and nation specific classifications, including opening hours, wheelchair access, and service availability. Being a crowd-sourced database, quality and coverage of the data has very large variation even within the same region. Because OSM is constantly updated, data is often more current than any other map datasets.

4.4 Transport System Data

4.4.1 OpenStreetMap Network Data

We used OSM data to conduct accessibility analysis for private cars and for walking connections in public transport analyses. In rural contexts, OSM has proven to be a particularly valuable data source due to its detailed coverage of local road networks, including smaller road types often missing from other large-scale open road data, such as NASA (gROADS) Global Roads Open Access Data Set, (see e.g. Ala-Hulkko et al. 2019). OSM road network is already highly complete and almost fully mapped in many countries, so it can reliably used for research and planning by its completeness, but however the data quality still vary substantially between countries and especially in mid population density areas (Barrington-Leigh & Millard-Ball 2017). Missing speed limits for roads were defined by using estimated typical travel speeds (Annex 1). The dataset provides necessary speed limit information to estimate driving times between any locations when conducting accessibility analysis in large scale (see Spiekermann et al 2013). To produce more realistic estimates for travel times population densities, turn time penalties of 7 seconds for right turns, 10 seconds for left turns as well as 3 seconds for passing intersections added to data (Jenelius and Koutsopoulos 2013).

4.4.2 General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) Scheduled Public Transport Network Data

For analysing regions providing open public transport in the General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) format – which is the standard format in the field in practice – public transport travel chain-based accessibility analyses were conducted. GTFS data is most often made available by regional authorities and/or public transport operators or their representative data managing partners. One of the main significance of GTFS datasets is that they provide the possibility to take schedules, waiting times and reasonable starting times of travel into account in accessibility analyses. From pilot regions in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Bulgaria, suitable GTFS data or other complementary data was not available, even though some other regions in these countries had GTFS data available.

Table 14. General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) data used for public transport analysis of pilot regions.

Area	Description	Link
Pilot region 1, Valle di Sole, Italy	Regional public transport data in GTFS format with yearly coverage. Published by Trentino Trasporti SpA.	https://www.trentinotrasporti.it/opendata/google_transit_extraurbano_tte.zip

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	Last accessed: 21.11.2025	
Pilot region 2, Sóller/Tramuntana, Spain	Transport database for regular public bus and train services on the Island of Mallorca. Published by Consorcio de Transportes de Mallorca (CTM). Last accessed: 20.01.2025	https://nap.transportes.gob.es/Account/Login?returnUrl=/Files/Detail/1071
Pilot region 3, North Ostrobothnia, Finland	National public transport data snapshot provided daily by Fintraffic. Last accessed: 21.01.2025	https://mobility.mobility-database.fintraffic.fi/static/finland_gtfs.zip
Pilot region 5, Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia	National public transport dataset covering rail and bus transport. Provided free of charge by the National Centre for Transport Management of the Republic of Slovenia through the national access point (NAP) following registration. Last accessed: 28.01.2025	https://www.nap.si/en/datasets_details?id=6fc3966a-5e3f-cf10-1df3-70d3af14d03d (registration required)

5. Harmonising and Integrating Data for Joint Data-Driven Analysis

5.1 Data Pipeline

We have designed a data pipeline that allows to automatize the analysis process. This data pipeline can manage and integrate various data sources and formats. The idea behind is to standardize the inputs ranging from Web Feature Services (WFS) and OpenStreetMap (OSM) to GeoJSON, Shapefiles, JSON, and CSV tables. This standardization is intended to ensure the consistent processing for geospatial and statistical data.

Figure 2 shows the flow from data collection to final output. The data pipeline starts by aggregating raw map data (Open GIS, OSM) with specific metrics like transport accessibility and network coverage. The workflow begins by pre-processing geographic shapes and enriching them with Point of Interest (POI) data to create detailed indicator layers. These layers feed into a core calculation engine that uses an LLM to compute the final report, while utilizing local storage to cache intermediate files. The resulting insights are ultimately outputted as generated reports and visualized on a public website.

Figure 2. Overview of the data pipeline and how it processes information.

The data pipeline uses a local caching strategy for several reasons. For example, external API calls, specifically GPT queries for text generation, can cause latency and extra costs. Saving processed descriptions locally reduces these issues. This approach ensures availability during external service interruptions.

5.1.1 OpenStreetMap Standards and Features

The pipeline strictly observes OpenStreetMap standards to secure geospatial fidelity. An ingestion engine interprets standard OSM tagging schemas, specifically *key:value* pairs, mapping physical features directly to internal data structures. The solution preserves

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topological relationships to process relations effectively. This approach renders boundaries and areas as cohesive units rather than disjointed geometries. Standard interchange formats allow the integration of open-source community changes, which keeps the base maps up to date. Furthermore, adherence to these standardized schemas facilitates precise semantic categorization across diverse data layers.

5.2 GeoServer Web Feature Service (WFS)

To share analytical results as a geographic vector data the GeoServer platform was used. Geoserver is open-source-based geographic information systems server platform enabling sharing and publishing geospatial datasets over the web using open geospatial standards. This allows users and applications to access and interact with the data beyond visualization. Derived datasets are made available on GeoServer through two different services: Web Map service and Web Feature Service. A Web Map Service (WMS) delivers on-the-fly map images—usually in raster formats like PNG or JPEG—allowing users use the shared data as a background map or visualization aid. In contrast, a Web Feature Service (WFS) provides access to the vector features themselves, returning raw spatial data such as geometries and attributes that can be saved, analyzed, edited and channeled into further data pipelines. More information on GeoServer and its uses can be found on <https://www.osgeo.org/> and <https://geoserver.org/>.

The SMART ERA GeoServer is openly available through the following addresses by any software or application capable to communicate with the interfaces:

- <https://ksimaps.oulu.fi/geoserver/wms>
- <https://ksimaps.oulu.fi/geoserver/wfs>

6. Overlay and Accessibility Methods

6.1 Multimodal Physical Accessibility Analyses

Accessibility to frequently used rural services, such as grocery stores and supermarkets, libraries and postal and automated parcel service points (Bogason 2023; Ramos-Truchero 2024) was measured to support the assessment of rural smartness in terms of mobility and transport, particularly regarding to car dependency at a local level. Target setting for this analysis is based on D2.1 *Indicator* Level of Analog Connectivity; and *Metrics* Percentage of households with access to regular postal service; Number of post boxes per square km & general public utilities. Again, the capability of rural areas to support electric vehicle (EV) usage with EV charger availability was measured to respond to the D2.1 *status indicator* 'low-carbon fuel vehicles'. (see, e.g., Noordveld et al. 2025; Mpoi et al 2023).

Geographic information science (GIS) based accessibility analysis use network data and travel 'cost' data such as travel time, travel distance or monetary cost of travel to evaluate how easily people can reach essential services by modelling actual/potential routes with road geometry and speed limit data enriched with other key attributes (Carroll et al 2021; Kotavaara et al. 2021). By combining detailed road network data with service locations and spatial population distribution, accessibility analyses are used to calculate the shortest travel times between origins and destinations, highlighting areas that are well or poorly accessible. This approach is widely used for planning and evaluating public services, infrastructure development, and spatial equity, especially in rural or mountainous regions where accessibility varies significantly with road conditions and terrain.

Accessibility analyses based on OSM data were carried out using a commercial geographic information system ESRI ArcGIS Pro 3.5, applying its 'Network Analyst' extension and its 'Closest Facility' function. For all accessibility indicators, services were obtained from OSM and transport accessibility for the rural population was measured using the most accurate European population scale provided by Eurostat, with a grid cell resolution of 1×1 km. This framework provides a multidimensional understanding of mobility and service provision in rural areas. The following subsections describe how data and analysis were used, and the table 13 below lists the openly provided variables.

In OSM 'highway' is the main key used for features representing all types of roads, street or path classification is a system used to categorize roads based on their importance and usage, from major motorways to small paths. It helps map data users, like navigation apps, understand which roads are most suitable for diverse types of travel. This classification is community-driven and continuously updated to reflect real-world conditions (OSM 2025).

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Table 15. Accessibility variables available for pilot regions in SMART ERA GeoServer.

Variable	Variable name in SMART ERA GeoServer	Definition
Car accessibility to grocery stores and supermarkets	CAR_ACCESS_GROCERY_STORE	The car travel time-based least-cost accessibility to the most accessible grocery store or supermarket based on OSM data and measured in minutes for a route from the centroid of the populated grid cells.
Car accessibility to libraries	CAR_ACCESS_LIBRARY	The car travel time-based least-cost accessibility to the most accessible library based on OSM data and measured in minutes for a route from the centroid of the populated grid cells.
Car accessibility to postal and automated parcel service points	CAR_ACCESS_POST	The car travel time-based least-cost accessibility to the most accessible postal and automated parcel service points on OSM data and measured in minutes for a route from the centroid of the populated grid cells.
Car accessibility to EV chargers	CAR_ACCESS_EV_CHARGER	The car travel time-based least-cost accessibility to the most accessible EV charger based on OSM data and measured in minutes for a route from the centroid of the populated grid cells.
Public transport accessibility to grocery stores and supermarkets	PUBLIC_T_ACCESS_GROCERY_STORE	The public transport travel time-based least-cost accessibility to the most accessible grocery store or supermarket based on OSM data and measured in minutes for a walk-transit-walk travel chain from the centroid of the populated grid cells.
Public transport accessibility to libraries	PUBLIC_T_ACCESS_LIBRARY	The public transport travel time-based least-cost accessibility to the most accessible library based on OSM data and measured in minutes for a walk-transit-walk travel chain from the centroid of the populated grid cells.
Public transport accessibility postal and automated parcel service points	PUBLIC_T_ACCESS_POST	The public transport travel time-based least-cost accessibility to the most accessible postal and automated parcel service points based on OSM data and measured in minutes for a walk-transit-walk travel chain from the centroid of the populated grid cells.

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Figure 3. Analysis of car accessibility to postal services for inhabited Eurostat 1x1 km population grid cells in pilot region 1, Valle di Sole, Italy.

Figure 4. Analysis of car accessibility to postal services for inhabited Eurostat 1x1 km population grid cells in pilot region 2, Sóller/Tramuntana, Spain.

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Figure 5. Analysis of car accessibility to postal services for inhabited Eurostat 1x1 km population grid cells in pilot region 3, Northern Ostrobothnia, Finland.

Figure 6. Analysis of car accessibility to postal services for inhabited Eurostat 1x1 km population grid cells in pilot region 4, Trebinje, East Herzegovina, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

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Figure 7. Analysis of car accessibility to postal services for inhabited Eurostat 1x1 km population grid cells in pilot region 5, Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia.

Figure 8. Analysis of car accessibility to postal services for inhabited Eurostat 1x1 km population grid cells in pilot region 6, Devetaki Plateau, Bulgaria.

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6.1.1 Accessibility Analysis with Public Transport Data

For pilot regions providing open public transport in the General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) format – which is the standard format in the field in practice – public transport travel chain-based accessibility analyses were conducted. GTFS data is most often made available by regional authorities and/or public transport operators or their representative data managing partners. GTFS data related tools of ArcGIS Pro 3.5 were utilized to enable generating scheduled transit travel chains including walking to and between stops and waiting times of connection routes.

One of the main significance of GTFS datasets is that they provide the possibility to take schedules, waiting times and reasonable starting times of travel into account in accessibility analyses. In our case, we wanted to assess multimodal travel chains that consist of walking from home locations represented by habituated grid cells to the public transport stops, traveling by public transport with needed changes and intermediate walking between stops and finally walking from the public transport stop to the service location.

To map travel times over defined temporal scope, accessibility calculated to as the fastest public transit connection between a grid cell and the closest service facility by one-minute intervals between 8:00 and 9:00 AM for typical weekdays outside of holiday seasons, and the shortest travel time was selected to represent travel time between the grid cell and the closest service (Kotavaara et al. 2021). GTFS data from year 2025 was used and reference dates for travels were Monday 3rd March 2025 for Finnish, Slovenian and Spanish and Monday 3rd November for Italian pilot region analyses. From pilot regions in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Bulgaria, suitable GTFS data or other complementary data was not available, even though some other regions in these countries had GTFS data available.

Calculation routines for public transport accessibility were automated with Python script. Produced public transport accessibility measures include also extreme outlier values where the travel consists largely or entirely of walking. These values can mainly be used to describe figures for the lack of suitable connections or as a comparative figure for accessibility by car.

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Figure 9. Analysis of public transport accessibility to grocery stores and supermarkets for inhabited Eurostat 1×1 km population grid cells in pilot region 1, Valle di Sole, Italy.

Figure 10. Analysis of public transport accessibility to libraries for inhabited Eurostat 1×1 km population grid cells in pilot region 1, Valle di Sole, Italy.

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Figure 11. Analysis of public transport accessibility to postal services for inhabited Eurostat 1×1 km population grid cells in pilot region 1, Valle di Sole, Italy.

6.1.2 Topological Quality and Corrections for OpenStreetMap Data

Routability of the geographical transport network data depends on the correct spatial topology i.e., connectivity of the various parts represented by lines (i.e., links) of road and street network. Transport network links need to be properly connected with accurate intersections enabling to generate valid routes without breaks or errors. As a community-based open-source data the spatial topological quality of OSM data is known to have large variation in topology between the links, even though completeness and positional accuracy tend to be high (see e.g. Sehra 2014; Raifer et al 2020).

To correct the topology for local and regional rural analysis, all road links were systematically examined for missing node connections. In cases where network segments crossed or touched without a shared node, an new node was inserted to ensure full network connectivity and to eliminate breaks in routability. This processing corrects the topological connectivity of the OSM-based transport network enabling large scale routing analysis without manual editing. However, artificial node creation, may cause some errors for example in the cases when bridges or overpasses are incorrectly planarised, resulting in false connections between different road levels that do not intersect in reality, which can produce invalid routing paths. In the cases of rural areas without large scale highway systems, tunnels or multilevel infrastructure the level of the errors can be considered to be marginal.

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6.1.3 Public Transport Turn Frequency Analysis

Using the GTFS datasets from each pilot region, a public transport turn frequency analysis was carried out. After selecting a representative weekday outside school holidays, all scheduled stop occurrences were aggregated in QGIS for each bus stop. This approach produced an effective visual representation of service intensity, which was subsequently published and shared on the public SMART ERA GeoServer platform.

Table 16. Number of public transport stops having turn frequencies analysed by pilot regions in SMART ERA GeoServer.

Pilot name, location	Name of turn density layer on SMART ERA GeoServer	Feature count
Pilot region 1, Valle di Sole, Italy	IT_aggregated_stops	129
Pilot region 2, Sóller/Tramuntana, Spain	ES_aggregated_stops	692
Pilot region 3, North Ostrobothnia, Finland	FI_aggregated_stops	7294
Pilot region 5, Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia	SI_aggregated_stops	194

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Figure 12. Visualization of public transport turn frequency in the pilot region 5, Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia.

6.2 Mobile Internet Availability

Digital connectivity refers to the ability of people and devices to access and share information via the internet and mobile networks. This relies on wired infrastructure, such as fibre optic cables, as well as wireless technologies like Wi-Fi and 5G. This access is crucial for participating in the modern digital economy, accessing online services, and facilitating communication and education. While few of the local, country specific data sources did provide a look into the mobile internet availability in the focused rural areas, we opted for a global, open dataset to use in the analysis for better consistency and coverage. To be able to create variable showing the rate of population where mobile internet is available, we used the Europe-wide 1 km by 1 km grid cell network of Eurostat population database, which has census-based information for each European Union member state's population. The grid also covers non-EU European countries, including reliable population data from older sources, such as for the pilot area in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Numerous operator-specific mobile network availability maps exist, alongside non-commercial national compilations of network availability and quality, such as those provided

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by Traficom (2025) in Finland and the Ministry for Digital Transformation and Public Service (2024) in Spain. Beyond national sources, commercial and community-based global network coverage datasets are also available providing more reliable access to information.

GSMA Intelligence, for instance, aggregates mobile network coverage information from participating service providers worldwide. Although GSMA Intelligence's datasets are high quality and include historical coverage information, they are not openly accessible and require purchase. OpenCellID describes itself as the largest global collaborative community project that collects GPS positions of cell towers. The main goal of the OpenCellID project is to serve as a data source for GSM localisation, where the database is published under an open content license with the intention of promoting free use and redistribution of the data. The measurements are taken by contributors who voluntarily submit cell measurements from smartphone applications. These measurements are available for any geographic location through an API interface.

fid	lat	lon	mcc	mnc	lac	cellid	range	samples	changeable	radio
8	45.495	13.499	219.0	2.0	131.0	128333003.0	1000.0	1.0	1.0	UMTS
9	45.496	13.499	219.0	10.0	6657.0	128333003.0	1000.0	1.0	1.0	UMTS
28	45.492	13.521	219.0	10.0	6657.0	154950733.0	1000.0	1.0	1.0	UMTS
30	45.493	13.505	219.0	10.0	202.0	584273.0	1000.0	1.0	1.0	LTE
31	45.493	13.509	219.0	10.0	6657.0	154945363.0	1000.0	1.0	1.0	UMTS
32	45.493	13.505	219.0	1.0	4100.0	192019462.0	1000.0	1.0	1.0	LTE

Figure 13. Exert from cell tower database for the pilot region 5, Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia.

Besides descriptive, locational and range data for each measured cell, the type of telecommunication technology is recorded for each cell tower. These include the three main evolutions of digital cellular networks: GSM, UMTS and LTE. GSM (Global System for Mobile Communications), also known as 2G (second generation), is a global standard for telecommunications and data transmission. UMTS (Universal Mobile Telecommunications System), also known as 3G, and LTE (Long-Term Evolution), also known as 4G, are generational improvements in terms of speed and coverage. The GSM standard, along with its subsequent upgrades, has an almost complete market share in telecommunications.

For the availability analysis each pilot region's cell tower database has been downloaded and geocoded. To account for the technological differences of useful range between GSM generations, a range filter has been utilized. A distance of 10 km for GSM (2G), 5km for UMTS (3G) and 2.5 km for LTE (4G) has been decided as a range maximum.

Table 17. Cell tower measurements in analysed data by pilot regions.

Pilot name, location	Cell tower measurements available
Pilot region 1, Valle di Sole, Italy	1343
Pilot region 2, Sóller/Tramuntana, Spain	268
Pilot region 3, North Ostrobothnia, Finland	1244
Pilot region 4, Trebinje, Bosnia and Herzegovina	242

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Pilot region 5, Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia	2567
Pilot region 6, Devetaki Plateau, Bulgaria	598

With the population data for each pilot area available in grid format, it is possible to determine the proportion of inhabitants covered by any generation of mobile internet coverage by creating a buffer zone for each cell tower and generation of GSM. This variable is openly shared through the SMART ERA GeoServer population layer with the following descriptions.

Table 18. Availability analysis-based data of 2G, 3G and 4G cellular networks for pilot regions in SMART ERA GeoServer.

Variable	Variable name in SMART ERA GeoServer	Definition
Availability of GSM (2G) cellular network	COVER_GSM	Binary field showing the availability of 2G cellular network within the grid cell.
Availability of GSM (3G) cellular network	COVER_3G	Binary field showing the availability of 3G cellular network within the grid cell.
Availability of GSM (4G) cellular network	COVER_4G	Binary field showing the availability of 4G cellular network within the grid cell.

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Figure 14. Coverage of GSM (2G) cellular network in Valle di Sole, Italy.

Figure 15. Coverage of GSM (3G) cellular network in Valle di Sole, Italy.

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Figure 16. Coverage of GSM (4G) cellular network in Valle di Sole, Italy.

Figure 17. Coverage of GSM (2G) cellular network in Sóller/Tramuntana, Spain.

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Figure 18. Coverage of GSM (3G) cellular network in Sóller/Tramuntana, Spain.

Figure 19. Coverage of GSM (4G) cellular network in Sóller/Tramuntana, Spain.

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Figure 20. Coverage of GSM (2G) cellular network in Northern Ostrobothnia, Finland.

Figure 21. Coverage of GSM (3G) cellular network in Northern Ostrobothnia, Finland.

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Figure 22. Coverage of GSM (4G) cellular network in Northern Ostrobothnia, Finland.

Figure 23. Coverage of GSM (2G) cellular network in Trebinje, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

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Figure 24. Coverage of GSM (3G) cellular network in Trebinje, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Figure 25. Coverage of GSM (4G) cellular network in Trebinje, Bosnia and Herzegovina.

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Figure 26. Coverage of GSM (2G) cellular network in Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia.

Figure 27. Coverage of GSM (3G) cellular network in Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia.

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Figure 28. Coverage of GSM (4G) cellular network in Šmarje-Padna, Slovenia.

Figure 29. Coverage of GSM (2G) cellular network in Devetaki Plateau, Bulgaria.

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Figure 30. Coverage of GSM (3G) cellular network in Devetaki Plateau, Bulgaria.

Figure 31. Coverage of GSM (4G) cellular network in Devetaki Plateau, Bulgaria.

6.3 Derived Local Spatial Variables on Infrastructure

A selection of derived variables based on deliverable (D2.1) titled Smartness Assessment methodology has also been made available on the SMARTERA GeoServer, based on datasets primarily used for accessibility and digital connectivity analyses. These variables offer an insight into the spatial patterns of the most important amenities such as bus stops, postal services and cell towers (Figure 32). Furthermore, a summary length of OSM roads where cycling is feasible, legal or possible facilitate the creation of new calculated variables.

Table 19. Available analysis-based derived variables for pilot regions in SMART ERA GeoServer.

Variable name in SMART ERA GeoServer	Definition
CELL_TOWER_DENSITY	Number of cell towers within grid based on OpenCellID data.
BUS_STOP_DENSITY	Number of bus stops within grid based on locally available GTFS datasets.
POSTBOX_DENSITY	Number of postboxes and parcel machines within grid based on OSM data.
POST_OFFICE_DENSITY	Number of post offices within grid based on OSM data.
CYCLING_NETWORK_ALL_LENGTH	Summarized length (in km) of roads where cycling is physically and legally possible within grid based on OSM data (using road categories: cycleway, footway, living_street, path, pedestrian, residential, road, secondary, secondary_link, service, steps, tertiary, tertiary_link, unclassified)
CYCLING_NETWORK_SELECTION_LENGTH	Summarized length (in km) of designated walking and cycling roads within grid based on OSM data (using road categories: cycleway, footway, living_street, pedestrian, residential).
CYCLING_NETWORK_RESIDENTIAL_LENGTH	Summarized length (in km) of designated walking and cycling roads within grid based on OSM data (using only the 'residential' category)

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Figure 32. Cell tower distribution in Northern Ostrobothnia, Finland.

7. AI-Based Interpretation of Data-Based Smartness Assessment

7.1 Introduction

Performing a manual analysis of all the information collected is not feasible, due to its complexity, the propensity to make errors, and its poor scalability. For this reason, we have borrowed methodology from the field of Geographical Intelligence (GI) to facilitate our goal of automatizing the smartness assessment. GI could be defined as the knowledge derived from collecting, processing, and analysing geographical information about places or regions, and it plays a crucial role in domains ranging from urban/rural planning and environmental monitoring to national security. With the help of GI, it is possible to perform analysis and provide results in the form of intelligence reports. These intelligence reports distil complex geographical data into human-readable insights that inform decision-making. For example, regional planning authorities could rely on comprehensive area reports to identify infrastructure needs, and policy makers use country-scale intelligence briefs to guide strategic initiatives.

However, generating such intelligence reports has traditionally been a manual and expertise-intensive task. Analysts must gather heterogeneous data (maps, demographic statistics, points of interest, remote sensing imagery, etc.), integrate and analyse these data, then compose a narrative that highlights key patterns and recommendations. This conventional process is not only time-consuming but also error-prone, potentially leading to delayed insights and inconsistent quality. Furthermore, the specialized knowledge required for geospatial analysis and tools often limit participation to experts, making the accessibility difficult for a broader audience. These challenges show us the demand for an automated solution that can generate high-quality geographical intelligence reports efficiently and accurately.

Recent advances in AI offer a promising path toward automation of report generation. In particular, the advent of LLMs and other AI techniques has enabled systems that comprehend data and produce natural language narratives with human-like fluency. LLMs have already demonstrated ability to interpret complex data patterns and generate coherent text in various domains. Prior research has explored using LLMs to summarize analysis results into reports. The findings indicate that general-purpose LLMs (e.g., GPT series) can effectively detect patterns in geospatial data and generate concise, readable reports, revealing the potential of AI for this task.

However, these kinds of reports also present critical limitations: generated outputs may suffer from factual inaccuracies (e.g., misreporting numerical data or spatial relationships) and variability across different runs. Ensuring the correctness and consistency of AI-generated content remains a major challenge, especially when dealing with sensitive or critical geographical intelligence information. Moreover, earlier attempts to integrate natural

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language interfaces with geospatial data often struggled with understanding user intent or producing reliable results, reflecting the complexity of bridging human language and precise geospatial data manipulation.

In this context, our work refers to the generation of knowledge obtained from collecting, processing, and analysing geographical information about specific places or regions. These intelligence reports are not just easy and cheap to produce but condense spatial data into readable summaries that support decision-making. Moreover, these reports can integrate and analyse these data before writing a narrative that presents patterns and recommendations.

The rest of this section is structured in the following way: The remaining sections of this text are structured to first provide the Rationale and Objectives for the work by outlining the need for automated GI report generation and the limitations of current LLM approaches. This leads into the Methodological Foundations, which grounds the work by reviewing related areas: AI in planning, GIS-AI integration, and general Data-to-Text Generation, detailing the strategies used to ensure factual accuracy. The next major part is the Technical Description of the Framework, which specifies the architecture and its components (Data, Planning, AI, User modules), along with the outputs (PDF Report and Interactive Web Application). This is followed by the Evaluation Strategy (Expert Review, Accuracy Audit, Stability Tests) and an assessment of Threats to Validity (data quality, LLM consistency). Finally, the Conclusion summarizes the system's achievements, its implications for spatial planning, and outlines future directions.

7.2 Rationale and Objectives

Recent progress in AI has opened new possibilities for automating report generation. LLMs and related techniques have made it possible for systems to interpret data and produce natural language text with human-like fluency. LLMs have already shown impressive performance in interpreting complex data and generating coherent writing across multiple domains. Some studies have investigated the use of LLMs to summarize spatio-temporal analyses into narrative reports. Their results indicate that general-purpose LLMs, such as the GPT family, can identify spatial patterns and produce readable summaries, showing strong potential for this application. However, current approaches still face notable difficulties. AI-generated content may contain factual errors, including incorrect numerical values or misrepresented spatial relationships, and the output can vary from one run to another.

7.3 Methodological Foundations

7.3.1 AI in Planning Environments

Digital tools for geographical planning are gaining ground across many regions. Recent works indicate that planners already rely on data-driven methods, though usage varies across professional backgrounds and institutional settings (Caprotti et al., 2024). In some

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cases, these tools already shape daily decision making, while in others they are still treated as optional add-ons. This uneven pattern often reflects differences in training, workflow traditions, and access to technical support.

Recent research reports similar tendencies, with several AI-based initiatives being tested in both large metropolitan areas and smaller cities. These efforts cover tasks ranging from automated mapping to scenario assessment. Many of them are still early experiments, yet they show how tightening links between planning practices and digital analysis can influence routine work across local administrations.

Digital twin projects are also appearing in multiple parts of the world. Work related to smart cities is one notable case, where virtual representations of key areas have been built to support monitoring, design adjustments, and public communication (Allan et al., 2025). Projects of this type help officials simulate changes in infrastructure, visualize proposed interventions, and share information with residents in a clearer way. Adoption rates differ, but interest in this direction continues to rise.

Additional studies take advantage of AI methods to support emergency response during severe weather. These investigations focus on rapid assessment of damage, prediction of risk zones, routing of emergency services, and real-time decision support. Accuracy still depends heavily on data quality, yet early findings show that these approaches can improve preparation and reduce delays during critical events.

Other work concentrates on extracting information from online public discussions. These methods help planners understand public concerns, detect recurring themes, and gauge reactions to proposed policies. Automated analysis of large volumes of comments is becoming more common as traditional surveys struggle to keep pace with the speed of online communication.

Recent reviews bring these strands together and describe steady progress across planning research. They also note that practical applications are already present in many cities, covering fields such as transport, environmental monitoring, heritage protection, and administrative coordination. Interest in more accessible digital planning tools continues to grow, especially in offices that aim to support quicker, more transparent decision making.

7.3.2 GIS and AI Integration

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) support the integration, processing, and visualization of spatial data across fields such as urban planning, transportation studies, and environmental analysis. Researchers have examined how certain tasks within these systems can be automated with AI, including routines that classify features, detect patterns, or assist with data cleaning (Zaroujtaghi et al., 2025). Interest in these approaches has grown as datasets become larger and more detailed.

Several reviews discuss how GIS tools are used within transportation studies, where they assist with routing, accessibility assessment, traffic analysis, and evaluation of public transport coverage. AI-supported methods add to this work by helping with large-scale

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classification, prediction, and pattern detection in ways that traditional manual processing cannot match.

A wide range of applications have been reported (Martinez-Gil et al., 2025). Remote sensing projects use GIS to organize satellite and aerial imagery for land use assessment, vegetation monitoring, and detection of rapid changes in terrain. Other studies extract flood depth estimates from images or reports shared on social media, offering quick situational awareness during severe weather events. Additional work focuses on reading information from street view imagery, including measurements of built features, road elements, and accessibility barriers.

There is growing interest in combining GIS with language models. This includes generating summaries of spatial patterns, producing explanatory text for maps, tailoring information for local administrations, and assisting with interpretation of complex geospatial datasets. Early experiments indicate that these combinations can support training, reporting, and routine analysis for users who may not specialize in geospatial methods.

7.3.3 Data-to-Text Generation

Our work can be viewed as a specific case of data-to-text generation, where the input consists of geospatial data and the output is a textual report. Data-to-text Natural Language Generation (NLG) has received extensive attention in the AI community (Lin et al., 2023). Its goal is to automatically produce fluent and informative narratives from structured data such as databases, knowledge graphs, or time-series records. Earlier systems were based on templates or hand-crafted rules. These methods ensured factual correctness but often produced repetitive and inflexible text. Recent advances in neural generation, particularly sequence-to-sequence models with attention and transformers, have improved this field. Trained on large corpora, these models learn to convert data representations into natural language and can generate varied and human-like descriptions.

A persistent issue in data-to-text generation is maintaining accuracy with respect to the source data while preserving natural phrasing. Neural models can sometimes invent or omit information. To address this, several strategies have been proposed, including conditioning generation on selected facts, using pointer mechanisms to copy exact values, and applying verification or post-editing procedures. Our framework incorporates several of these strategies. First, key facts are explicitly chosen through the analysis module before text generation. This selection is based on statistical significance and practical relevance; for instance, if a village has 50% fewer healthcare facilities per capita than the national average, that fact is marked for inclusion. Second, the LLM prompt is designed to present these selected data points in a tabular or bullet format so that the model has direct access to the exact values to mention. This reduces the risk of numerical inaccuracies. Third, a post-generation verification process checks the output text, extracting numeric values and claims for comparison with the original data. Any mismatch leads to regeneration or correction. This multi-step approach draws inspiration from fact-checking workflows.

Evaluation of text quality is another essential component. Common metrics in NLG include BLEU and ROUGE, which measure content overlaps with reference texts, and human

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evaluation focusing on coherence, fluency, and usefulness. In our case, since each regional report is unique and reference texts are not always available, we rely more heavily on expert review and factual accuracy assessments. We also include a measure of factual coverage, quantifying how many selected facts are correctly represented in the generated report. This measure is particularly relevant for geographical intelligence reports, where omitting a key data point could have significant consequences. Our evaluation setup aligns with recent research that stresses the importance of assessing both factual fidelity and linguistic quality.

7.4 Technical Description of the Framework

The framework that we have built offers a configurable tool for assessing rural smartness without technical expertise. It integrates heterogeneous data, preprocesses them for AI to use, and delivers results through a PDF report, an interactive web application, and a REST API. Its modular design allows for straightforward extension and integration with data providers and AI engines.

7.4.1 Architectural Model

A conceptual view of the framework is shown in Figure 33. Each module operates independently, with limited permissions and access. For instance, the user cannot directly access the raw data sources or the AI engine. Such an approach helps maintain the system's high stability and significantly improves its security, particularly when using commercial data sources and expensive AI systems.

The architecture consists of four modules, each with clear boundaries to maintain stability and reduce operational risk. Please note that the modules are domain-agnostic; only adapters change when applying the pipeline in other settings.

- **Data module:** collects and preprocesses raw inputs from remote and local sources, computes the indicators, and stores harmonized datasets.
- **Planning module:** triggers data updates based on configured schedules or user requests.
- **AI module:** manages the prompting strategy, caches responses, and ensures that generated text remains tied to validated values.
- **User module:** provides an interactive web application, API endpoints, and PDF report generation.

This architecture reduces hallucinations through strict access control and data flow rules: the AI module receives only harmonized indicators prepared in advance, cannot read raw sources, cannot select data, and cannot infer missing values. Each run references a single dataset snapshot chosen through scheduled or user-triggered updates, which prevents mixed versions inside one output. Cached responses keep repeated requests consistent and auditable. Limited user access to internal services blocks prompt injection and accidental disclosure, and generated text can always be traced to specific indicators with timestamps and provenance, which limits speculative statements.

Figure 33. Conceptual architecture of our solution.

The working mode then can be seen as a high-level system architecture. The flow begins on the left with External RAW Data Sources, which feed information into a central Data Module. This Data Module acts as a primary connector, linking to a Planning Module below it (for orchestration and scheduling) and pushing information into a central Local Data repository. This Local Data storage serves as the core integration point for two downstream components: a User Module at the bottom, which handles user interaction and retrieval, and an AI Module at the top. The AI Module processes the stored information by connecting to an external AI Engine (represented by a brain-and-gear) to perform intelligent analysis or computation.

7.4.2 PDF Reports

The framework can generate structured PDF reports containing the final index, weight distribution, individual indicator values, and AI-generated interpretations. Files are produced with the FPDF library and can be fetched via the REST API by specifying the area, model, and JWT credentials.

The report shown in Figure 34 includes:

- a header defining the area and input parameters,
- a short section summarizing key elements affecting the index,
- the computed index with a comparison against neighbouring locations, and a detailed breakdown of each indicator including values, weights, and optional descriptions.

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These reports are suitable for policymakers, local councils, and automated pipelines that require structured output for further processing.

Figure 34. View of the PDF report generated for Alavieska, Finland.

7.4.3 Interactive Web Application

The interactive web application provides a clean interface for selecting a region, inspecting its indicators, and exploring map layers. Users can zoom, filter POI categories, and view the smartness index together with its components. The web application also includes direct links to the API, enabling machine-to-machine access for municipalities or research groups. A sample screen is shown in Figure 35.

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Figure 35. View of the interactive web application for the visualization of the smartness indicators.

7.5 Evaluation Strategy

While the framework architecture is established, the formal evaluation phase has not yet been conducted. A rigorous validation protocol is scheduled to be implemented over the pending two years of the project lifecycle. This phase is designed to ensure the reliability, accuracy, and safety of the AI and Data modules before full deployment.

The planned evaluation strategy is multi-dimensional, targeting four key areas of system performance:

- **Expert Reviews.** Domain experts inspect the generated reports and confirm whether the statements correspond to the underlying data and whether the structure aligns with expectations for planning or policy reports. Experts will specifically screen for hallucinations, i.e., plausible but factually incorrect statements. The goal is to ensure that every claim made by the AI is supported by the ingested evidence.
- **Accuracy Audit.** Automated tools verify datasets, metadata links, and report statements. Accuracy audits are repeated whenever datasets are updated. We will verify that all data points are correctly linked to their metadata sources. This audit trails the data lineage, guaranteeing that every generated insight can be traced back to a specific, immutable data file.
- **Stability Tests.** Given that LLMs may produce slightly different outputs across runs, the evaluation should consider each prompt multiple times and compare differences. The structured fact-selection and constraints might ensure high stability. The testing

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will verify that the architecture's structured fact-selection layer effectively forces the LLM to adhere to defined boundaries, minimizing the creativity typically associated with generative AI in favour of reliability.

- **Longitudinal Consistency.** When applied to the same region across different time periods (e.g., yearly updates), the framework should be able to assess whether recurring statements remain consistent unless data changes justify updates. In this way, our framework should distinguish between a change in narrative caused by model instability (which is a failure) and a change caused by legitimate shifts in underlying data (which is a feature).

7.6 Threats to Validity

Some factors can influence how reliable the solution is. The points below clarify how the results should be read and where sensitivity to data quality or local conditions may appear.

- Our solution relies on external datasets that vary in coverage and overall detail. Missing fields, outdated entries, and uneven contributions to sources like OSM can shift indicator values in ways that do not match real conditions. Areas with limited mapping activity are more exposed to this issue.
- The precision of the results depends on the quality of geospatial boundaries and the accompanying metadata. Administrative polygons, coordinate systems, and attribute tables can contain inaccuracies or irregularities that pass through the processing steps. Since rural datasets are maintained by different institutions, each with its own interpretation of settlement limits, mismatches can weaken the comparability of indicators.
- Explanations produced with LLMs require regular review to ensure that the text stays consistent with the evidence used in the analysis. Providers update their models, alter default parameters, or adjust typical output styles, which can affect tone and level of detail. Safeguards reduce unsupported statements, but stable long-term use still needs periodic validation against ground-truth information and clear documentation of versions, prompts, and settings.
- The workflow contains several stages that can shift if some assumptions change. Data acquisition, filtering, spatial operations, and text generation all depend on tools and libraries that may evolve. Version updates, changes in pre-processing routines, or alterations in file structures can influence reproducibility. Keeping detailed records of software versions and configuration files, helps reduce drift over time.

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These points show where careful checks are useful and where future refinements can strengthen the framework. Regular reviews of data sources, spatial definitions, and processing steps might support consistent use across different regions and data conditions.

7.7 Lessons Learnt

In this section, we have presented our framework designed to generate high-quality GI reports. It combines data analysis with NLG to deliver timely and accurate geographical intelligence. Our solution can ingest heterogeneous data from multiple national GIS sources, extract meaningful information, and compose a coherent report that communicates findings clearly to the user. Through preliminary experiments, our solution achieved factual accuracy and produced narratives approaching the quality of human experts, significantly reducing the manual effort and specialized expertise normally required to create such reports.

The success of our approach carries several implications. From an operational viewpoint, it might allow organizations to produce consistent and up-to-date intelligence reports for any region of interest with minimal user intervention. This capability is valuable for monitoring rapidly changing conditions and maintaining situational awareness across diverse locations. From an academic perspective, our framework provides a concrete solution to persistent issues in automated report generation, particularly the problem of maintaining data fidelity while using LLMs for natural language output.

The results will show that structured prompting combined with verification steps can effectively reduce factual errors in a domain where precision is critical. Moreover, the formalization of this process offers a foundation for continued research, framing GI report generation as an optimization task with AI components integrated into the analytical pipeline.

Future directions will include advanced anomaly and causal analysis, real-time data integration, multilingual reporting, domain fine-tuning, recommendations grounded in evidence, and deployment with feedback loops in operational settings.

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Annex 1 – Speed Limits for Missing Data in the OpenStreetMap (OSM) Road Network

Table 20. Speed limits for missing data in the OpenStreetMap (OSM) road network.

OSM road class	Speed limit (estimated)
bridleway	4
busway	60
cycleway	4
footway	4
living_street	30
motorway	120
motorway_link	120
path	4
pedestrian	4
primary	100
primary_link	100
residential	30
secondary	80
secondary_link	80
service	30
steps	4
tertiary	80
tertiary_link	80
track	10
track_grade1	10
track_grade2	10
track_grade3	10
track_grade4	10
track_grade5	10
trunk	100
trunk_link	100
unclassified	60
unknown	30